

Streaked weaver bird, which prefers a wet habitat, was the most abundant and most serious pest (Table 1). Red munia was the least serious pest. Whitebacked munia and spotted munia preferred dry conditions, and caused little damage.

VCT has large areas of rice fields interspersed with sugarcane fields at a 5:1 ratio, and 0.5 to 1 ha marshy patcher covered with *Typha* sp. The patches of sugarcane and the marsh determined bird distribution and concentration because they provide roosting, nesting, and shelter. We therefore recorded panicle damage in rice fields at various

Table 2. Panicle damage^a on rice fields at various distances from marsh and sugarcane, VCT, Mandya, India.

Time	Panicle damage (%)					
	Among fields ^b			Within a field ^c		
	< 10 m	10 to 20 m	> 20 m	Edge	Center	Rear
May 1985	37	0	0	45	<1	<1
May 1985	35	0	0	47	<1	<1

^aAt each location, ± panicle damage is from 15 randomly chosen units. ^bDistances from patches of marsh and sugarcane. ^cEdge = 4 rows adjacent to marsh or sugarcane plot; centre = in between edge and rear; rear = last 4 rows of rice from marsh or sugarcane.

distances from marshland and sugarcane fields. Table 2 shows that 35-37% of bird damage was within 10 m of

sugarcane and marsh. Damage was greatest in rice immediately adjacent to sugarcane and marsh. *J*

Soil and Crop Management

Nutrient management in late kharif rice

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We studied nutrient management in late kharif rice at TNAU in 1975. Soil had pH 8.1, ECe 0.2 mmho/cm, low N, high P and K, 88 ppm Fe, and 4 ppm Zn. All plots received the recommended 120-26.4-50.4 kg NPK/ha. The experiment was in split-plot design with IR8, IR20, and Bhavani each sown in main plots on 15 Aug, 1 Sep, and 15 Sep. Subplots were control, 30 kg N/ha, 30-6.6 kg NP/ha, 50 kg ferrous sulfate/ha, and 50 kg ferrous sulfate and 25 kg Zn sulfate/ha.

Grain yield decreased when sowing was later than 15 Aug (see table). The 15 Aug crop had greater leaf area index, longer panicles, and more filled spikelets than other crops. IR20 yielded more than Bhavani and IR8 in the 15 Sep sowing. Applying Fe and Zn increased yield 20% over that of the control. Sowing date and fertilizer application were not significantly interactive, indicating that grain yield of the 15 Sep crop would not reach that of the 15 Aug crop, even with additional fertilizer application. *J*

Influence of sowing date, variety, and fertilization on grain yield in Tamil Nadu, India.

Sowing date	Variety	Yield (t/ha)					Mean
		30 kg N	30 kg N 6.6 kg P	50 kg ferrous sulfate	50 kg ferrous sulfate 25 kg Zn sulfate	Control	
15 Aug	IR8	4.5	4.3	3.9	4.4	3.5	4.1
	IR20	4.6	4.7	4.9	5.1	4.3	4.8
	Bhavani	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.5	4.7	5.0
	Mean	4.7	4.7	4.6	5.0	4.1	4.6
1 Sep	IR8	2.5	2.0	1.9	2.4	2.2	2.2
	IR20	2.8	2.6	2.9	3.0	2.5	2.8
	Bhavani	3.2	3.3	3.0	3.6	2.7	3.2
	Mean	2.8	2.6	2.6	3.0	2.5	2.7
15 Sep	IR8	0.9	0.9	1.0	1.4	0.8	1.0
	IR20	2.7	2.9	2.8	3.0	2.6	2.8
	Bhavani	1.7	2.1	1.8	2.2	1.9	1.9
	Mean	1.8	1.9	1.9	2.2	1.8	1.9

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Sowing date for photoperiod-sensitive Caribe 7

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Caribe 7 grows in low-lying fields where deep water may prevent other varieties from being grown. It is photoperiod

Performance of Caribe 7 at different sowing dates, Havana, Cuba.

Date	Yield ^a (t/ha)
15 Apr	4.5 ab
15 May	4.4 b
15 Jun	5.5 a
15 Jul	2.5 c

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P = 0.05).

sensitive and is planted to mature when water recedes and soil begins to dry. We determined yield potential of Caribe 7 then sown on 15 Apr, 15 May, 15 Jun,

and 15 Jul.

Yield increased slightly from the Apr to Jun plantings, after which it decreased sharply (see table). Caribe 7

flowered between 13 and 25 Oct, when there were about 7 sunshine hours, irrespective of planting date. *ℓ*

Response of lowland rice to zinc fertilizer

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We studied the effect of Zn sulfate on IR50 grain yield at TNRRI in Jun-Sep 1984. Soil was an alluvial clay loam (Adanur series) with 0.9 ppm available DTPA-extractable Zn, 35 meq cation

Effect of Zn application on rice yield, Aduthurai, India.

Treatment (kg Zn/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
0	3.1
2.75	4.1
5.75	4.7
8.25	4.7
11	4.7
13.75	4.7
16.5	4.7
CD	0.2

exchange capacity, 100 g, and pH 6.9.

The experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications. Zn sulfate was incorporated at 0, 2.75, 5.75, 8.25, 11, 13.75, and 16.5 kg Zn/ha just before transplanting. Recommended NPK was applied.

Applying Zn significantly increased grain yield. IR50 responded up to 8.25 kg Zn/ha (see table). *ℓ*

Rice-Based Cropping Systems

Irrigated rice-based crop sequences for eastern Madhya Pradesh

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Rice is a major Jun-to-Oct crop in eastern Madhya Pradesh. Most land is fallow after rice, but some areas have assured irrigation. We evaluated different irrigated crops to follow rice in rabi (Nov-Apr) and summer (Mar-Jun) in 1981-82 and 1982-83 (Table 1,2). Soil was a clay loam. Medium-duration (125-130 d) Kranti and Asha were transplanted from Jul to mid-Aug. Rice received 80-23-25 kg NPK/ha and yielded 44.5 t/ha. Rabi crops were sown from mid-Nov to mid-Dec and harvested from mid-Mar to late Jun. Summer crops were planted from mid-Feb to mid-Mar and harvested from mid-May to mid-Jun. Fertilizer rates for rabi and summer crops are in the tables.

Cereals and vegetables also performed well. The study suggested that extending irrigation to the area could increase cropping intensity 200-300%. *ℓ*

Table 1. Grain and green pod yield of rabi and Summer season crops following rice, 1982-83, Bilaspur, India.

Crop sequence	Rabi				Summer			
	Fertilizer (kg/ha)			Yield (t/ha)	Fertilizer dose (kg/ha)			Yield (t/ha)
	N	P	K		N	P	K	
Rice -wheat - mungbean	100	22	24.9	3.3	20	17.6	16.6	0.9
Rice - gram - okra	20	13.2	16.6	2.5	50	11	20.75	7.7 ^a
Rice -mustard - mungbean	20	13.2	0	0.7	20	17.6	16.6	1.2
Rice - arhar - cowpea	60	8.8	16.6	1.1	20	17.6	16.6	5.2 ^a
Rice - safflower - cowpea	60	17.6	0	1.0	20	17.6	16.6	4.2 ^a
Rice - potato - mungbean	150	35.2	33.2	39.0	20	17.6	16.6	1.3
Rice - onion - mungbean	100	22	83	31.0	20	17.6	16.6	0.9
Rice - garlic - mungbean	100	22	83	6.2	20	17.6	16.6	1.2
Rice - chili (Jawla)	125	22	41.5	18.7	20	17.6	16.6	-
Rice - chili (Japanese longi)	125	22	41.5	10.3	20	17.6	16.6	-

^a As green vegetable.

Table 2. Grain yield of rabi season crops following rice, Bilaspur, India.

Crop sequence	Fertilizer dose (kg/ha)			Yield (t/ha)	
	N	P	K	1981-82	1982-83
Rice - wheat	100	22	24.9	3.4	2.4
Rice - cotton	60	13.2	12.45	1.8	2.0
Rice - groundnut	20	13.2	16.6	2.4	3.0
Rice - maize	100	22	24.9	3.2	3.3
Rice - sorghum	80	17.6	24.9	1.9	2.6
Rice - black soybean	20	35.2	16.6	1.0	1.7
CD (0.05%)				0.5	0.6